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Examination Malpractice: Causes and Effects on Students' Academic Performance. A Study of Some Selected Secondary Schools in Sokoto State

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ABSTRACT

Examination not only serves as a feedback for the trainer to ascertain the level of knowledge acquisition but also serves as a measure of knowledge retention by the trainee. Any misconduct or irregularity distorts the true outcome of the learning process. Therefore this research will be focusing on the disturbing trend of Examination Malpractice and students' academic performance in some selected Secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis with the view to find out the real causes of examination malpractice among the students. The research not only defined the concept of examination malpractice but also identified the types or forms, the causes or reasons, the effects as well as the ways to eradicate it. For the purpose of this research study, descriptive survey research design will be adopted. However, with this method of research personal interview and close observation will be used to collect data and inferential statistics that would serve as method of data analysis to determine the relationship between the examination and malpractice. The sample for the study area will comprises of the six (6) secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis. The sample technique adopted for the purpose of this research work will be random sampling. This consists of 50 students to be selected based on population from each school which will give us a total of three hundred (300) respondents. The research is expected to produce results that would use as a measure to address the menace of examination malpractice in our secondary schools.

Keywords: Examination, Malpractice, Academic Performance

INTRODUCTION

Education, being a process of teaching and learning is evaluated through examination at the end of the learning period. Daily Trust (2024) says that education is a necessary process through which young adults are equipped to lead productive lives according to their talents and interests. Through education, learners are not only taught, trained, and adequately guided to acquire relevant skills and knowledge but also how to adapt to acceptable public life. To some people, education is seen as a means of overcoming handicaps, achieving greater equality, and acquiring wealth and status for all. It is also often perceived as a place where children can develop according to their unique needs and potentials, with the purpose of developing every individual to their full potential, (Daily Trust 2024). The early years of schooling focuses around developing basic interpersonal communication and literacy skills. Later, education turns towards gaining the knowledge and skills needed to create value and establish a livelihood. Also, people

pursue education for its own sake to satisfy innate curiosity, out of interest in a specific subject or skill, or for overall personal development. According to (Ijadeniji 2017) education could be formal or informal. Formal education occurs in a structured environment whose explicit purpose is teaching of students. Usually, formal education takes place in a school environment with classrooms of multiple students learning together with a trained, certified teacher of the subject. Whilst informal learning occurs in a variety of places, such as out of school time, in youth programmes at community centres and even village squares. Informal learning does not follow a specified curriculum and may originate accidentally, sporadically, in association with certain occasions, from changing practical requirements. It is not necessarily planned to be pedagogically conscious, systematic and according to subjects, but rather unconsciously incidental, holistically problem oriented, and related to situation management and fitness for life.

In the traditional African educational system, teaching and learning were basically practical. The students learned orally and through close observation of their master. In fact it was through imitation, no issuance of certificate to prove completion of course of study since the society was interested in skill acquisition and practical demonstration of the arts learned. Definitely, there was no need for certification, since education was viewed as a means to an end and not an end in itself (Akanni and Odojin, 2015). It is against this background that this research intends to study examination malpractice: causes and effects on students' academic performance with selected secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis as a case study.

Statement and Justification of the Problem

It is clear that examination malpractice tends to confer undue advantage or undeserved grade to the perpetrators of the act. Again, it may be committed by not only the candidates but also by other bodies charged with the responsibilities of examination management. Undoubtedly, examination malpractice has been a social problem for decades, but the rate and manner it is perpetrated nowadays calls for serious concern. The rate of this crime has become so widespread that there is virtually no examination anywhere at all levels and outside the formal school system that there is no one form of illegal practice or another, (Nnam & Inah, 2015). Examination malpractices are common everywhere and every examination season witnesses the emergence of new and ingenious ways of cheating, (Nnam and Inah, 2015) (Anzene, 2014) This alarming rate of involvement into examinations malpractice is rapidly increasing than ever before in every public schools, the examination bodies are the West African Examination council (WAEC). Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (JAMB). National Examination council (NECO). These have led to cancellation of results in public examinations and suspension dismissal of supervisors. The major forms of examination malpractice reported are: Impersonation; bringing in materials like books, papers, substituting worked scripts, collusion in the examination hall (copying); mass/organized cheating involving assistance from teachers with collaboration of supervisors and copying direct from blackboard (Danbaba and Ezeuduji, 2018). This trend in examination malpractices is inimical to academic development and advancement and needed to be drastically addressed hence the immediate urge and need for conducting this research to ascertain the impacts of examination malpractice on students' academic performance in selected secondary schools in Sokoto State Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are as follows:

1. To examine the causes and effects of examination malpractices on students' performance.
2. To find out teachers, students collaboration in Examination malpractice
3. To provide guidelines on how to tackle the problem of examination malpractice in senior secondary schools in Sokoto State

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following questions;

- i. Do parents collaborate with schools to perpetuate examination malpractices?
- ii. What effect could examination malpractice have on students' academic performance?
- iii. Are teachers and supervisors involved in examination malpractices?

Review of Related Literature

Various literatures are captured in this research, based on the conceptualization of the examination malpractice and students' academic performance.

Academic Performance

Many researchers has been discussed the different factors that affects the student academic performance in their research. There are two types of factors that affect the students' academic performance. These are internal and external classroom factors and these factors strongly affect the students' performance. Internal classroom factors includes students competence in English, class schedules, class size, English text books, class test results, learning facilities, homework, environment of the class, complexity of the course material, teachers role in the class, technology used in the class and exams systems. External classroom factors include extracurricular activities, family problems, work and financial, social and other problems. Research studies shows that students' performance depends on many factors such as learning facilities, gender and age differences, etc. that can affect student performance (Anzene, 2014). It equally stated found that the most important factor with positive effect on students' performance is student's involvement in exam malpractice. If the students can read well without depending on any form of exam malpractice, it increases the performance of the students (Danbaba and Ezeuduji 2018). The performance of the student is affected by examination malpractice; it is possible to see upright and seriousness as a variable which may be positively related to performance or the student in open leaning. A major distinction of this study from previous studies is that it focuses on open commitment to learning without dependence on any form of examination malpractice (Nnam and Inah 2015).

Examination Malpractice

Many problems confronting our educational system today are the issue of examination malpractice. Examination malpractice is a kind of conduct that violates the acceptable laid down rules and regulations of our educational system. On the other hand, examination

malpractice is any wrong doing before, during or after any examination (Akanni and Odofin 2015).

Although one may not be able to rule out examination malpractice in the past, the current trend is alarming and calls for stakeholders to come out with urgent solutions in order to save the nations' educational sector from collapsing, Whereas, in the past, students are hiding the acts, now they advertise it by buying booklets to write exam outside the hall to by bribing teachers to smuggle them with the written answers. It has become a prolific business enterprise branded with the special class aided and abetted by corrupt teachers and supervisors, supported by parents who will pay for the fees involved. According to Ijabadeniji (2017) defined examination malpractices as an improper and dishonest act associated with examination with a view to obtaining unmerited advantage. Again, Oredein (2015) argue that examination malpractice is described as the massive and unprecedented abuse of rules and regulations pertaining to internal and external examinations, beginning from the setting of such examinations through the taking of the examinations, their marking and grading to the release of the results and the issuance of certificates.

Forms of Examination Malpractice

Anzene (2014) outlined the following forms of examination malpractice:

- Storage of answers inside mobile phones which is very rampant nowadays
- Creation of examination special classes or centres outside the main examination centres.
- Connivance with examination body unfaithful staff to release live questions to the students after receiving payments from them
- Bribing supervisors to turn blind eyes, and allow teachers to take away question papers and prepare answers outside the exam hall and bring it to students to copy in the hall.

Certainly, the above forms or classes of examination malpractice being indulged by the Perpetrators were caused by one thing or another. Hence we turn to the next sub – topic.

Reasons for Examination Malpractice

Several reasons have been advanced as the factors of examination malpractice. They Include: (Paul 2013)

- Societal Moral Decadence: The standard of moral virtues among the youths is falling

- Economic Hardship: poverty and poor remuneration of teachers in the country has made some of the teachers to be indulged in undignified forms of making money.
- Psychological Factor: Some students are expressing fear and lack of confidence in their own performance hence they indulge in malpractice to avoid being stigmatized as lazy and failures.
- Poor teaching and learning environment: Most of the schools in the country lack adequate teaching materials and infrastructure for proper learning to take place. Since students are ill-equipped, therefore majority of them resort to examination malpractice to pass.
- Parental pressure on children: Some parents are having too much expectation on their children to produce a good result; they can resorts to some tactics to enhance their children success through the means of malpractice.

Effects of Examination Malpractice

- It leads to production of quacks of educationalists who cannot defend their Certificates
- Many upright students have been denied opportunities by corrupt ones who as a result of examination malpractice have better scores and grades
- Government and examination bodies in the country are spending large sums of money to combat examination
- It demoralized and discourages hard working students to have low self-esteem, because they are no longer sure of their capabilities.

Population of the Study

The study areas are;

- Nana Girls Secondary School,
- Sultan Bello Secondary School,
- Sultan Attahiru Ahmadu Secondary School,
- Giginya Memorial Secondary School Sokoto,
- Government Girls College Sokoto
- Government Day Secondary School Arkilla

Sample Size and Sampling Procedure

It is impractical to collect data on the whole population, considering the size, as well as the time, available to the researcher, hence the need to select a sample that represent the whole population because of time, budget and accuracy for the study. Simple random sampling method have a guarantee that every programmed locations have the same probability of being chosen for the sample and it lets each and every part of the population equal chance of being selected. The samples for the study are examination malpractice and 300 students are randomly selected.

LEVEL	SELECTED SCHOOLS	TARGET RESPONDENTS	TOTAL
A	Nana Girls Secondary School Sokoto	50	50
B	Sultan Bello Secondary School Sokoto	50	50
C	Sultan Attahiru Ahmadu Secondary School Sokto	50	50
D	Giginya Memorial Secondary School Sokoto	50	50
E	Governments Girls College Sokoto	50	50
F	Government Day Secondary School Arkilla	50	50
	TOTAL	300	300

METHODOLOGY

For the purpose of this research study, descriptive survey design was adopted which is concern with the collection of data or the purpose of describing and interpreting the existing condition. However, with this method of research design, a questionnaire was used to collect data and inferential statistic would serve as

method of data analysis to determine the relationship between variables. This research is designed to last for six months so as to have adequate data. The population of the study was comprised of the students of the six (6) secondary schools in Sokoto. The sample technique adopted for the purpose of this research work was stratified random sampling. The research produces results that would use as a measure to address the existing problems of examination malpractice bedevilling our schools.

Table 2.1: Distribution of Questionnaire

Schools	Distribution of Questionnaires	Returned Questionnaires	Percentage of Questionnaires Returned
NGSS SOKOTO	50	45	90
SBSS SOKOTO	50	38	76
SAASS SOKOTO	50	40	80
GMSS SOKOTO	50	41	82
GGC SOKOTO	50	50	100
GDSS ARKILLA	50	38	76
Total	300	252	90.1

Source: Questionnaire Administered 2025

The table 2.1 shows the distribution of questionnaires to six (6) selected secondary schools in Sokoto states. In all 300 questionnaires were administered among the six (6) schools while only 252 were completed

Table 2.2: The linkage between Examination Malpractice and Academic Performance in the selected secondary schools

S/N	Options	Responses	Percentage
1.	The examination malpractice affects the Academic performance of students	205	81.34
2.	Are teachers and supervisors involved in examination malpractice	230	91.26
3.	Do Parents collaborate with schools to perpetuate examination malpractice	240	95.23
4.	Do lack of good learning materials and infrastructures increase the rate of examination malpractice	200	79.36

Source: Questionnaire Administered 2025

A table 2.2 show that examination malpractices have affects the academic performance in six (6) selected secondary schools. As the response show, it will be seen that majority of respondents 205 representing (81.34) percent attributed that examination malpractice have affected students' academic performance. Also confirmed that 230 respondents representing (91.26) percent agreed that teachers and supervisors are involved in examination malpractice. Similarly 240 respondents representing (95.23) percent agreed that parents are collaborating with school teachers to perpetuate exam malpractice in their schools. Lastly 200 respondents representing (78.36) percent believed that lack of good learning materials and infrastructures are attributed to the rate of examination malpractice. Conclusively, the table revealed that there is serious linkage between the students and examination malpractice in the selected secondary schools.

Table 2.3: Factors aiding examination malpractice in senior secondary schools

S/N	Options	Responses	Percentage
1.	Societal moral decadence	190	75.39
2.	Economic hardship	200	79.36
3.	Psychological factor	195	77.38
4.	Parental pressure on the children	205	81.34
5.	Poor learning materials	190	75.39

Source: Questionnaire Administered 2025

Table 2.3 shows the impact of the factors aiding examination malpractice in some selected senior secondary schools in Sokoto state. The results show that while 190 respondents representing (75.39) percent said societal moral decadence has relationship with examination malpractice. 200 respondents representing (70.36) attributed the menace of examination malpractice to economic hardship and poor remuneration to teachers. 195 respondents representing (77.38) percent believed that psychological factor leads to examination malpractice in our schools. 205 respondents representing (81.34) percent attached acts of examination malpractice to the undue pressure of parents to their children to produce good grades. Similarly, 190 respondents representing (75.39) percent attributed the risen cases of examination malpractice on poor atmosphere of learning, and lack of good infrastructures. Connivance with supervisors, low self-esteem on the part of students and parental pressure from the parents to the children to produced good grade are few among many factors that are aiding examination malpractices in our schools.

CONCLUSION

Examinations are designed to take place under a set of standards and procedures. When these set of standards are breached, it is often in the form of malpractice. Examination malpractice is any form of dishonest or fraudulent behaviour carried out by students during an examination to gain an unfair advantage. Examination malpractice may result in individual passing exams without the necessary skills and knowledge, leading to a workforce with inadequately nonqualified and inexperienced workers. When students resort to cheating during examination, the true assessment of knowledge and skills becomes compromised, leading to a decline in the overall quality of education. Finally, examination malpractice undermines the values of honesty, integrity and fair competition in the educational sector, leading to a lack of trust and respect for academic achievements and degradation of educational standards.

RECOMMENDATION

Government can develop social programs designed to change how parents view their roles in this era by encouraging a good parental upbringing, poor parenting plays a vital role in examination malpractice. Parents should also cut their children some slack and allow them to pursue their true passions, rather than forcing them to fulfil their own unfulfilled dreams or a predetermined career path. Promulgation and enforcement of examination malpractice (prohibition) laws must be enhanced. If fully implemented, it will serve as deterrent to teachers, supervisors, and students in the malpractice business. The remuneration of teachers must be increase, so also examination supervisors must also be fully paid to dissuade them from financial inducements from parents and students. Lastly, Employment of qualified teachers at all levels of education must be adhered to The need to have qualified teachers in our schools cannot be overemphasized.

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